

OCCUPATIONAL HAZARDS OF WOMEN HEALTHCARE WORKER: AN EXPLORATORY

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Abstract

An occupational hazard refers to the risk, injury or accident that occurs at the workplace. Healthcare workers had encountered numbers of occupational hazards at their workplace on besides their promotion and preventive services at the health settings; there are physical, biological, chemical, reproductive and psychosocial occupational hazards encountered by the healthcare workers. The health and well-being of the workers are affected by the occupational hazards and which led to the development of various psychosocial problems, infectious diseases, musculoskeletal disorders and reproductive health problems.

Keywords: *occupational hazards, healthcare workers, health settings*

Introduction

Healthcare workers plays a significant role on the promotion and prevention of health for the population, they provide services directly and indirectly as a doctor, nurses and as a nursing assistance, laboratory technicians, physiotherapist, radiographer, community health workers, ASHA workers and even medical waste handlers (Awodele et al., 2014; Joseph, 2016). Healthcare workers are employed in primary, secondary and tertiary levels of health settings, the World Health Report stated that there are 59 million (approx.) health workers worldwide and in India healthcare workers are about 4.3 million serving a population of 1.2 billion (Senthil et al., 2015). Health setting is regarded as one of the most hazardous places and occurs numbers of job-related injuries and infections among the workers, the International Labor Organization (ILO) reported that every 15s, 153 employees experienced injuries related to work and premature mortality is increasing year by year as a result of occupational related injuries (Mona et al., 2019).

Occupational hazards can be understood as a risk, accidents and harm that an individual experiences at the workplace (Awodele et al., 2014), in other words “potential risk to the health of a person emerging from an unhealthy environment” (Osaretin Owie & Apanga, 2016). The health worker besides their role on the promotion and preventive in healthcare, they are exposed to different types of occupational hazards viz., biological hazards, chemical hazards, physical hazards, reproductive hazards and psychosocial hazards. Inappropriate workers safety precautions, unsafe and unhealthy environment and inappropriate disposal of bio-chemical waste are some of the factors responsible for workplace hazards, absenteeism, lack of interest and unproductive job performance are the negative impact of workplace hazards (Akinbode, 2018).

Statement of the problem

Occupational hazards are becoming a growing social issue as a result of the covid-19 pandemic. There had been little research on this topic in the North-eastern state and Mizoram, and the pandemic had increased the occupational hazards of female healthcare workers, affecting both their physical and mental health. Women work in a variety of roles and responsibilities in the healthcare sector, including doctors, nurses, midwives, radiographers, laboratory technicians, administrative workers, and others (Lantz, 2008). However, as the number of women working in healthcare grows, they continue to face a variety of issues and challenges at work (ALobaid et al., 2020). This study has explored the most common occupational issues, physical and psychosocial hazards that women healthcare workers encountered in the workplace.

Objectives of the study

- To identify the challenges faced by women healthcare workers in Aizawl district, Mizoram
- To assess the coping strategy adopted by the women healthcare workers in Aizawl district, Mizoram.

Review of Literature

Tan, C. C. 1991; Harrington, 1982; Chhabra, 2016; DiBenedetto, 1995; Arasi Senthil et al., 2015; Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018; Pornpimol Kongtip et al., 2018; Rawlance Ndejjo et al., 2015; Rim & Lim, 2014; Favero, 1987; Moore & Kaczmarek, 1990 has studied the biological hazards faced by the healthcare workers in the hospitals. Also, the health workers engaging in radiation and surgery departments reported more skin disease (Report of Health and safety in Medical Laboratories). In addition, the laboratory technicians are prone to infectious diseases like Tuberculosis (TB), Hepatitis B, HIV/AIDS, skin diseases, and cancer and needle syringe injury with an average rate of 1 in 3 months (Arasi Senthil et al., 2015). The needle syringe injury has led many infectious diseases, and related death to the health workers (Di Benedetto, 1995) and laboratory workers are exposed to certain hazardous chemicals and materials which can have long term health effects (Harrington 1982). Laboratory technicians are at a higher risk of infection with Hepatitis B as they regularly handle blood and contaminated items (Favero, 1987). While conducting a clinical examination, assisting the incapable patients, drawing body fluids samples from the patients and treating wounds nurses and doctors are also prone to biological infection, performing other activities such as transporting the chemical waste, cleaning, disinfecting and working on contaminated places can cause other health worker exposed to biological hazards (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018). Biological hazards are classified into two categories; allergic/toxic agents and 'zoonosis' agents, which can be transmitted to humans from animals and other infectious diseases. Infectious diseases can be transmit from needle syringe injury and physical contact with the patients. Allergic and toxic agents are those chemicals and radiations that are used in the hospital for treating their patients (Rim & Lim, 2014). Workers in the radiology department have a higher chance of developing cancer and other skin diseases (Chhabra 2016). Health workers in surgery and anaesthesia department reported that they have skin problems due to exposure radiation, blur vision and eye irritation due to inadequate lightning in the operation room (Pornpimol Kongtip et al., 2018).

Assadi, (2013), Figà-Talamanca, (2000) Gonzalez, (2011), Anderson & Goldman, (2020) has studied the occupational hazards faced by women healthcare workers based on the survey report of Occupational Reproductive Hazards for Female Surgeons in the Operating Room and found that the reproductive hazards are prevalent among female surgeon who is engaging in the operating room who are regularly in contact with anaesthetic gases, radiation and surgical smoke which can increase the rate of infertility and pregnancy complications, the working conditions, long hours of working, long hours of standing and night duty can also affect the outcome of the pregnancy. Thus, the reproductive age mothers need to be aware of the chemical hazards that can affect reproductive health. A comparative study was conducted among the administrative workers and clinical workers of the pregnant mother, performing heavy physical activities and using tobacco is related to low birth weight. The study revealed that clinical workers have a higher chance of having reproductive hazards like menses disorder as they are more often exposed to chemical Assadi, (2013) and 'aesthetic gases', 'antineoplastic drugs', and some 'physical agents', particularly 'ionizing and non-ionizing radiation', are found to be common in the healthcare settings as compared to other types of the work environment. These are one of the main factors resulting in reproductive hazards of women healthcare workers. When the pregnant mothers are exposed to 'aesthetic gases' there is a risk to damage the foetus and results into miscarriage, chromosomes abnormalities and exposure to 'ionizing and non-ionizing radiation' causing birth complications and the possibility of developing cancer (Figà-Talamanca, 2000). The study also found that performing heavy physical activities and using tobacco is related to low birth weight. The clinical workers have a higher chance of having reproductive hazards like

menses disorder compared to administrative workers, and clinical workers are more to chemical exposure (Assadi, 2013).

Further, the hazards that health workers are exposed to and reproductive health effects of the health workers and pregnant mother was studied by Gonzalez, (2011) and found that biological hazards, physical hazards and chemical hazards all have the potential threat affecting reproductive hazards of the health workers with and increasing infertility rates, causing miscarriage, low birth weight and development disorder to pregnancy. Besides, the performance of physical activities such as lifting and carrying heavy objects during pregnancy, direct contact with the patients and cleaning of the patient room can cause severe allergy to the women health workers.

Methods

The study adopted descriptive design and purposive sampling is adopted and quantitative data is collected using structured questionnaire. The quantitative data collected through structured questionnaires is processed and analysed with the help of Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software v26. Tables are used to present the data, which are represented using simple statistics such as percentage and mean calculations.

Results & Discussion

There are three stages in the result analysis. There are physical hazards analysis, psychosocial hazards analysis and the coping strategies analysis.

Table No 1 Physical hazards

Sl. No.	Factors	Responses (N=100)
1.	Body aching	80 (80 %)
2.	Headache	79 (79 %)
3.	Eye problem	59 (59 %)
4.	Bone fracture	6 (6 %)

Source:

Computed Figure in parentheses are percentage

Firstly, the health workers' roles require lots of physical input/activity to take care of their patients and it affects their physical health in many ways. The maximum of the respondents reported that headache (80%) and body aching (79%) are the major factor contributing to the occurrence of physical hazards among the women healthcare workers followed by eye problem (59%) and bone fracture (6%).

Table No 2 Psychosocial Hazards

Sl. No.	Factors	Responses (N=100)
1.	Anxiety	45 (45 %)
2.	Insomnia	44 (44 %)
3.	Assaulted by patients	43 (43 %)
4.	Emotional Insecurity	37 (37%)
5.	Social withdrawal	36 (36 %)
6.	Low Self-eEsteem	36 (36 %)
7.	Aggressiveness	34 (34 %)
8.	Poor interpersonal relationship	31 (31 %)
9.	Helplessness	28 (28 %)
10.	Depression	17 (17 %)

Source: Computed Figure in parentheses are percentage

Secondly, factor of psychosocial hazards is categorised into 9 items such as insomnia, anxiety, assault by patients, emotional insecurity, social withdrawal, low self-esteem, aggressiveness, poor

interpersonal relationship, helplessness and depression. The maximum of nearly half of the respondents reported that anxiety (45%), insomnia (44%) and assaults by patients (43%) are the main causes of psychosocial problems among the respondents. More than one third of the respondents reported that emotional insecurity (37%), social withdrawal (36%), low self-esteem (36%) and aggressiveness (34%) are encountered by the respondents. Further, less than one third of the respondents had encountered helplessness (28%), and depression (17%).

Table No 3 Coping strategies

Sl. No.	Hazards	Coping skills	Mean
1.	Physical hazards	Sleep and relaxation	3.3
		Medication	2.6
		Regular physical exercise	2.5
2.	Psychosocial hazards	Prayer & meditation	3.9
		Ventilate negative feelings	2.9
		Average mean score	3.04

Source: Computed

Thirdly, the coping strategies adopted by the women healthcare workers were identified, prayer and meditation is mostly adopted coping skills in times of psychosocial hazards with a mean score of 3.9 and ventilate negative feelings with a mean score of 2.9 and on the physical hazards coping skills, sleep and relaxation is a commonly practiced by the women healthcare workers with a mean score of 3.3 and followed by medication and regular physical exercise with a mean score of 2.6 and 2.5 each. The average mean score represented that the coping skills adopted by the women healthcare workers are relevant with an average mean score of 3.04.

Conclusion

In conclusion, occupational hazards is regarded as one among the global issue affecting healthcare workers all over the world. In spite of the fact that the contribution of the healthcare workers is significant, and numbers of human life's are rest upon them; while caring and treating for their patient's, the health and well-beings of the healthcare workers are neglected often and the sufferings of the healthcare workers are left unnoticed and untreated. Apparently, the unsettled physical and psychosocial issues leads into destructive coping behaviours like drug addiction, alcohol addiction, suicidal ideations and other mental health issues. On the other hand, though being encountered the healthcare workers many times do not disclosed the information because this could hinder their professional progression. Therefore, the safety needs and precautionary measures of the health care workers is an urgent international concern that call for convergence of prothong intervention. Hence, the implementation of the regulations should be effective covering the entire health care settings, the promotion, protection and prevention of the health of the healthcare workers are to be so as to mitigate the numbers of injuries and lose of the lives of healthcare workers due to occupational hazards.

References

- Ahmad, A. (2017). Prevalence and predictors of occupational stress among quarry workers in rural Rajasthan, India. *Journal of Public Mental Health*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/JPMH-03-2017-0008>
- Anderson, M., & Goldman, R. H. (2020). Occupational Reproductive Hazards for Female Surgeons in the Operating Room: A Review. *JAMA Surgery*, 155(3), 243–249. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamasurg.2019.5420>
- Asante, J. O., Li, M. J., Liao, J., & Huang, Y. X. (2019). The relationship between psychosocial risk factors, burnout and quality of life among primary healthcare workers in rural Guangdong province: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 8, 1–10. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-4278-8>

- Assadi, S. N. (2013). Is being a healthcare worker a risk factor for women's reproductive system? *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 4(7), 852–857.
- Awodele, O., Popoola, T. D., Ogbudu, B. S., Akinyede, A., Coker, H. A. B., & Akintonwa, A. (2014). Occupational Hazards and Safety Measures Amongst the Paint Factory Workers in Lagos, Nigeria. *Safety and Health at Work*, 5(2), 106–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2014.02.001>
- Bernhardt, J. H. (1990). Potential Workplace Hazards to Reproductive Health Information for Primary Prevention. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, & Neonatal Nursing*, 19(1), 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.1990.tb02525.x>
- DiBenedetto, D. V. (1995). Occupational hazards in the health care industry. *AAOHN Journal*, 43(2), 131–137.
- Favero, M. S. (1987). Biological Hazards in the Laboratory. *Laboratory Medicine*, 18(10), 665–670. <https://doi.org/10.1093/labmed/18.10.665>
- Figà-Talamanca, I. (2000). Reproductive problems among women health care workers: Epidemiologic evidence and preventive strategies. *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 22(2), 249–260. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.epirev.a018037>
- Gonzalez, C. (2011). Occupational Reproductive Health and Pregnancy Hazards Confronting Health Care Workers. *AAOHN Journal*, 59(9), 373–376. <https://doi.org/10.1177/216507991105900901>
- Joseph, B., & Joseph, M. (2016). The health of the healthcare workers. *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 20(2), 71. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5278.197518>
- Jrm, B., Ctj, H., & Jk, S. (2016). The Prevalence of Work-Related Stress Complaints among Healthcare Workers for the Disabled Participating in a Workers' Health Surveillance Program. *Occupational Medicine & Health Affairs*, 4(6), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2329-6879.1000256>
- Mona, G. G., Chimbari, M. J., & Hongoro, C. (2019). A systematic review on occupational hazards, injuries and diseases among police officers worldwide: Policy implications for the South African Police Service. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, 14(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-018-0221-x>
- Muzzi, M., Pawlina, C., & Schnorr, G. P. (2018). Prevalence of stress in health workers in the context hospital. *Psychology and Behavioral Medicine Open Access Journal*, 0, 15–21.
- Okeafor, C. U., & Alamina, F. E. (2018). A Qualitative Study on Psychosocial Hazards among Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Health Facility in South-South Nigeria. *Annals of Ibadan Postgraduate Medicine*, 16(1), 23–29.
- Osaretin Owie, H., & Apanga, P. A. (2016). Occupational Health Hazards Prevailing among Healthcare Workers in Developing Countries. *Journal of AIDS & Clinical Research*, 7(8). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-6113.1000596>
- Rim, K. T. (2017). Reproductive Toxic Chemicals at Work and Efforts to Protect Workers' Health: A Literature Review. *Safety and Health at Work*, 8(2), 143–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2017.04.003>
- Senthil, A., Anandh, B., Jayachandran, P., Thangavel, G., Josephin, D., Yamini, R., & Kalpana, B. (2015). Perception and prevalence of work-related health hazards among health care workers in public health facilities in southern India. *International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 21(1), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1179/2049396714Y.0000000096>